

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP SINGLE LAP ADHESIVE JOINT

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Introduction

To reduce weight of aircraft...

- Application of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) to airframes
- Replacing mechanical fastening with adhesive bonding

Issue: CFRP has a significantly noble galvanic potential relative to the metal

In the Metal-CFRP adhesive joint of the aircraft structure; Galvanic corrosion of the metal affects the mechanical properties

In this study

Object: Quantitatively evaluating the strength of metal-CFRP adhesive joint

- Aluminum-CFRP single lap adhesive joints without corrosion were prepared to obtain reference data
- Strength and failure mode of the joints were evaluated by performing tensile shear tests and observing the failure surface after the test

Experiment Method

Tensile Shear Test ; In order to evaluate the strength of the joint

- Failure surface was visually observed to determine the failure mode
- Strain gauges were attached and the strain of the CFRP substrate was measured

Acoustic Emission (AE) Measurement ; In order to investigate the failure process

- Performed simultaneously with the tensile shear test
- We focus on Amplitude and Hits (number of occurrences for AE waves)

Aluminum	CFRP	Adhesive
Extra Super Duralumin (A7075P-T6)	Quasi-isotropic CFRP Laminate (T800S/3900-2B) Stacking Sequence : [45/0/-45/90] _{2S}	Two-liquid Mixed Type Epoxy Adhesive (Araldite Standard) Curing Condition : Room Temperature, 24 h → 60°C, 45 min

Results and Discussion

Strength and AE Behavior

- Average tensile shear adhesive strength was 11.8 MPa
- High amplitude AE waves (more than 60 dB) were detected just before failure
- Cumulative hits increased rapidly just before failure

Failure progressed relatively rapidly

Strain-Displacement Behavior of the CFRP Substrate

- Strain of Strain Gage i side shows a positive increase; Tensile stress was induced
- Strain of Strain Gage ii side shows a negative increase; Compressive stress was induced

Stress differs on the front and back of the substrate

Failure Surface Observation

Interfacial failure was dominant

It is due to the low interfacial strength between adhesive and substrate

Conclusions and Future Work

In this study

The Strength of the metal-CFRP adhesive joint was experimentally surveyed

For Aluminum-CFRP single lap adhesive joints without corrosion, strength, failure process and failure mode were evaluated

- AE measurement during the tensile shear test; It is considered that the failure of the joint progressed relatively rapidly
- Strain measurement of the CFRP substrate; It was found that stress difference occurs on the front and back of the substrate
- Interfacial failure was mainly observed on the surface after the test; Suggesting that the interfacial strength between adhesive and substrate is low

In the future

It is necessary to survey the relationship between metal corrosion and joint strength